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Review Paper

The Evolving Role of Medical Science Liaisons in India: Bridging the Gap Between Science and Medicine

Dr. Neeraj Hiremath, Dr. Sudhanshu Shukla*, Pratiksha Bhandare

Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy Hubballi-580031

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ABSTRACT

Medical science liaison is a field-based profession whose main responsibilities are to facilitate the exchange of unbiased scientific information between the medical community and the pharmaceutical or surgical companies, and to foster collaborative relationships with Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) by providing medical and scientific support, supporting sales and marketing colleagues according to companies' strategic objectives in exploring business opportunities. MSLs can provide specialized information and assistance to the health care professionals in India. The inherent constraints that the Indian healthcare sector faces, such as poor infrastructure and geographical dispersion, need adaptation and individualized methods. Given the changing healthcare landscape and the increased emphasis on worldwide operations, including emerging countries, the MSL function in India has the potential for significant growth and expansion. Looking ahead, MSL's growing presence in India will be centered on marketing support, with an emphasis on collaborative partnerships and scientific support to contribute to better patient outcomes and pharmaceutical innovation.

INTRODUCTION

An MSL is field-based scientific expert appointed by a Pharmaceutical, biotechnology, medical device, healthcare management business. The MSL's major role is to build, promote, and encourage collaboration between organization they represent and thought leaders, thereby advancing in medicine and research. Ideally, the

companies' MSL team reports to the medical affairs department. In 1967 Upjohn Pharmaceuticals created Medical Science Liaisons (MSLs) to meet the need, for field staff who were trained in matters and capable of building relationships with Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) in certain study areas. Companies have used several titles for this function over time, including Medical

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Sudhanshu Shukla

Address: Department of Pharmacy Practice, KLE College of Pharmacy Hubballi-580031

Email ✉: sshukla8104315419

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Liaisons, Regional Scientific Managers, Scientific Affairs Managers, Clinical Liaisons, Medical Managers.¹

How does MSL differ from a Pharmaceutical Sales Representative

A salesperson offers sample to physician.

Representative markets items by combining key brand messages and adhering to package labeling rules. Representatives usually collaborate closely with physicians who directly tend to patients' needs. Sales agents strive to meet individual and regional sales targets for the drugs they promote. The representative can only disclose information that is consistent with the approved and current package insert (PI) or product label.

An MSL Provides Medical Information.

Impartial scientific engagement and a thorough discussion of illness conditions and treatment options. MSLs exchange information and data, learning through peers and sharing rather than selling or pushing. MSL focuses on scientific research and education. A sales representative's primary clientele consists of clinically trained physicians, but they also collaborate with scientists undertaking research and education. MSLs frequently interact with pre-clinical researchers, some of whom have PhDs. The MSL's performance and goals are often oriented at long-term outcomes. MSLs never rely on sales data, don't offer samples, and are rarely evaluated by call frequency.¹

Importance of MSL

Medical Science Liaisons (MSLs) help to bridge the gap between pharmaceutical firms, healthcare practitioners, and researchers. They act as the pharmaceutical industry's scientific face, linking corporations with medical professionals such as key opinion leaders, healthcare decision-makers and clinical investigators. MSLs give highly reliable, clinical information and unbiased scientific information, establishing and maintaining significant scientific credibility with

external specialists. They also contribute relevant, timely, and practical insights to the organization, helping clinicians by discussing the most recent scientific advancements.² MSLs are experts at explaining intricate scientific and medical concepts to a variety of stakeholders. They build and preserve close relationships with important outside experts in their shared therapeutic field, acting as a reliable conduit to external parties and easing communication between clinical advancement and business success. Additionally, MSLs gather information that guides business strategy in areas like product development and market access, greatly enhancing the expansion and prosperity of pharmaceutical companies.³

Important factors for MSL operations are shown in Table 1.⁴

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The MSL's primary task is to create and develop professional relationships with external experts (key opinion leaders) while also facilitating an exchange of scientific knowledge, perspectives, needs, and possibilities.⁵ The medical science liaison acts as a liaison between the investigators and the manufacturer of the medicine or technology during the study's development, grant submission, and execution. The medical science liaison is well positioned to provide product training while simultaneously supporting the investigation team in maintaining under budget and project schedules.⁶ A medical science liaison (MSL) is responsible for disseminating medical information in a timely and responsive manner, fostering Collaboration with key opinion leaders (KOLs), facilitating the interchange of unbiased scientific information between the medical community and the company, and supporting sales and marketing initiatives.^{7,8} MSLs build and strengthen relationships with KOLs by offering medical and scientific support, organizing scientific activities for customer groups, and informing clinical peers about the most recent

scientific advancements.⁹ They also help to generate clinical and scientific material, write medical articles, train speakers, and arrange publications.¹⁰ MSLs are field-based specialists that have extensive knowledge of disease states and products represented by their company and rivals, as well as a thorough understanding of research, regulatory, and medical education environments and processes.⁶ Their exceptional academic background and scientific aptitude provide them authority and sway when interacting with other medical professionals.

KOL Management

An essential part of a pharmaceutical company's life cycle process for a particular drug or product is KOL management. When their patients have an abundance of medication options, physicians frequently seek knowledge and advice from other key opinion leaders. Regional Medical Advisors (RMA) serve an important role in providing scientific and technical support to key opinion leaders (KOLs) while also maintaining professional and credible connections. This guarantees access to updated medical and scientific knowledge. Additionally, KOLs value MSLs who are Knowledge of internal corporate processes is required to access specialized resources and research opportunities within the MSL's company. Nonbranded educational slide decks provided by MSLs are highly valued by KOLs. To improve MSL-KOL relationships, it is important for MSLs to avoid aggressiveness, leading questions, and a commercial spin. Advanced MSL training should include communication, networking skills and interpersonal relationship skills, advocacy for KOL needs, extensive scientific training, and understanding of healthcare systems and reform. The finest MSLs modify their interactions to meet the needs of the medical professionals with whom they deal. ^[9,10].

QUALIFICATIONS

The educational and professional qualifications required to become a Medical Science Liaison (MSL) vary, but most MSLs have advanced degrees such as a PharmD, PhD, or MD. The majority of MSLs hold a PharmD degree, while approximately 10% have a PhD and 1-2% have an MD. Other health professionals and scientists can also fill these positions, including nurses and professionals with medical, scientific, or business backgrounds. The MSL role requires advanced training and expertise in specific Oncology, Neurology/Neuroscience, Rare Diseases, Immunology, Cardiology, Haematology, Endocrinology, and Dermatology are some of the therapeutic fields. MSLs must create and maintain peer-to-peer connections with healthcare experts and key opinion leaders, provide current safety and efficacy data, and perform scientific activities for client groups. ^[7]

Challenges in India

MSLs, in India face challenges in the healthcare sector due to the geographical expanse, inadequate infrastructure and limited internet speeds and supporting facilities. ¹⁰ These hurdles often make it difficult for MSLs to conduct face to face visits and effectively communicate scientific messages through digital platforms. To tackle these obstacles MSLs can focus on establishing relationships with opinion leaders who can offer valuable insights.¹¹ Moreover, they can explore communication methods like utilizing the internet to connect with doctors in areas while considering the limitations of internet speeds and infrastructure.¹ It is crucial for MSLs to adapt their approach and leverage their expertise to provide information and support to healthcare professionals, in India¹² By understanding the needs and challenges of the healthcare landscape MSLs can devise strategies to navigate through these barriers successfully.

Impact on the health and pharmaceutical industry

The positive impact of MSL on medical practice, collaborative research, and product development can be seen through a variety of examples and case studies. For example, Moss et al. They conducted a survey of key opinion leaders (KOLs) with diabetes and found that MSLs are valuable resources that KOLs find, help them stay abreast of project issues and save their time MSL also play an important role in supporting research projects, and contribute to increase researcher-initiated research and collaborative research efforts¹¹ In addition, MSLs participate in the development of advanced training programs to enhance the skills and knowledge of experienced MSLs, such as a forum for communication skills and communication strategies, thus emphasizing clinical value creation practice¹² This example illustrates how MSLs positively influence clinical practice, collaborative research, and product development by raising scientific knowledge and valuable contributions.

Future trends and opportunities in India

The growth and expansion potential of MSL services in India is high with growing healthcare infrastructure and increasing focus on global operations, including emerging markets.⁸ with expanding field medical communication teams worldwide, and India is no exception to this trend. MSL's role in India will be largely commercial support-oriented, focusing on establishing collaborative relationships with Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) and providing medical and scientific support.⁹ This includes providing non-scientific information exchanging favours between physicians and pharmaceutical companies, supporting sales and marketing efforts¹⁰ In addition as the healthcare infrastructure in India continues to evolve, MSLs have the opportunity to play an important role in

differentiating between physicians and pharmaceutical companies in solution, support research and innovation, and improve patient outcomes.^{11,1}

CONCLUSION

The Medical Science Liaison (MSL) bridges the gap between pharmaceutical companies and the healthcare industry in India. Originally formed to build relationships with key opinion leaders (KOLs), MSLs are now also ambassadors for science, providing neutral and reliable information to promote research, collaboration and product development Despite the challenges, the positive impact of medical practice and research collaboration on MSLs highlights their importance in the changing healthcare marketplace. Looking ahead, MSL's increasing position in India will be increasingly focused on commercial support, with a focus on collaboration and scientific support to help improve patient outcomes and clinical innovation

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